

Effect of nitrogen level on grain yield of rice under bush fallow continuous rice cultivation in high rainfall

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Upland soils in Liberia are generally low in nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). We evaluated the yield response of some upland rice varieties to applied N under bush fallow continuous rice cropping systems in the high-rainfall forest zone.

Trials were conducted first in 1980 on Acrisol soils at Suakoko after thick bush was cleared during the 1979 dry season. Nitrogen levels were tested in main plot trials and replicated varietal tests were in subplots. Trials at the same site were conducted in the 1981 and 1982 wet seasons. In 1980 and 1981, N as urea was applied in two split doses. In 1982 it was applied in three splits. In each trial 18 kg P/ha was applied at seeding and 33 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied at time of N application in split doses.

In 1980, after the bush was cleared, all 5 varieties yielded more than 1.0 t/ha without fertilizer N. With application of 20 to 40 kg N/ha, 2 to 3 t grain yields/ha could be harvested. Some varieties lodged at 40 kg N/ha. Yield increased with level of N applied.

Grain yields in 1981, regardless of N levels or varieties, were lower than in 1980, but grain yields increased with N levels.

Similarly, third-year grain yields at all N levels and varieties were lower than in the first and second years (see table).

Local rice variety LAC23, which was grown in all 3 years, was used to estimate the yield response surface as follows:

$$1980: \hat{Y} = 1648.0 + 48.87x - 0.33x^2$$

$$1981: \hat{Y} = 798.7 + 17.01x - 0.10x^2$$

$$1982: \hat{Y} = 715.9 + 15.96x - 0.005x^2$$

(where \hat{Y} = grain yield in kg/ha, and x = N level in kg/ha).

The equations indicated that the yield response to applied N in LAC23 was almost linear. However, the estimated yield increase (kg/kg N) decreased with

Yield response of rice varieties to nitrogen under bush fallow continuous rice cultivation in high rainfall area of Liberia.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha) in various nitrogen levels (kg/ha) and years						Mean
		0	20	30	40	60	90	
<i>1980</i>								
LAC23	95	1.6	2.5	—	3.1	—	—	2.4
4418	93	1.0	2.8	—	3.6	—	—	2.5
MRC172-9	86	1.1	3.1	—	3.3	—	—	2.5
IR2035-108-2	94	1.1	2.5	—	3.0	—	—	2.2
ROK3	88	1.5	1.8	—	2.4	—	—	1.9
Mean		1.3	2.5	—	3.1			
LSD (0.05) N × V			0.2					
<i>1981</i>								
LAC23	95	0.8	1.1	—	1.3	1.5	—	1.2
4418	93	1.0	1.3	—	1.4	1.7	—	1.3
C22	99	0.7	0.9	—	1.4	1.7	—	1.2
IRAT132	92	0.7	0.8	—	1.0	1.3	—	1.0
Mean		0.8	1.0	—	1.3	1.5		
LSD (0.05) N × V			0.14					
<i>1982</i>								
LAC23	104	0.7	—	1.2	—	1.7	2.1	1.4
SEL IRAT 194/1/2	86	0.7	—	1.0	—	1.5	1.9	1.3
LS(1)-19-1-1	107	0.5	—	0.9	—	1.5	1.9	1.2
TOX502-2SLR-LS2-5B	97	0.5	—	0.8	—	1.2	1.9	1.1
Mean		0.6	—	1.0	—	1.5	2.0	
LSD (0.05) N			0.12					
LSD (0.05) V			0.16					

increasing N levels as follows:

Year	N levels (kg/ha)	Yield increase (kg/kg N)
1980	20	42
	40	36
1981	20	15
	40	13
	60	11
1982	30	16
	60	16
	60	16

Yield data indicate that for the first rice crop after bush fallow 20–40 kg N/ha may be needed to harvest more than 2.0 t rice/ha. However, 1.0 t rice/ha could be harvested without added N. For the second and third rice crops, more than 40 kg N/ha may be needed to harvest 1.5 to 2.0 t rice/ha.

The economics of applied N in upland bush fallow continuous rice cropping systems have yet to be defined. N application alone will not maintain grain yields. Decreasing organic matter content, exchangeable cations, CEC, and soil pH may cause low yields in succeeding rice crops.

Nitrogen management for transplanted rice in rainfed lowlands

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A major cause of low transplanted lowland rice yields in India is low fertilizer inputs, especially nitrogen fertilizer. Uncontrolled water supplies in lowland areas cause erratic fertilizer response. We sought to develop appropriate technology for N fertilizer application for transplanted rice grown on rainfed lowlands.

The experiment was conducted at the Rice Research Station, Malan, during the 1980 wet season. Soil was loamy with pH of 5.85; medium levels of organic carbon, available N, and P; and high available N, and P; and high available K. Three-week-old Himdhan seedlings were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing. At puddling time, before transplanting, 40 kg each of P₂O₅ and K₂O/ha were applied.

Applying 60 kg N/ha significantly in-

creased grain yield compared to the no-nitrogen check. Response to nitrogen applied under various treatments ranged from 6 to 40 kg grain/kg N (see table). highest grain yield was recorded when urea supergranules were deep-placed in the root zone. Neem cake and lac-coated urea produced equal grain yields that were lower than those with supergranules. When nitrogen was applied as equal splits of urea at planting and panicle initiation, grain yield was much lower than that in the other treatments. Farmyard manure-coated urea did not perform well. Urea applied at planting produced lowest grain yields.

The experiment showed the benefits of applying nitrogen to lowland rice and the effectiveness of urea supergranule deep placement. □

Grain yield, nitrogen response, and some agronomic characters as influenced by different nitrogen treatments in transplanted rice under rainfed lowland conditions, Malan, India.

N source	Time and rate (kg/ha) of N application			Efficiency of nitrogen (kg grain/kg N)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)
	Planting	Panicle initiation	Total				
Control	0	0	0	—	1.1	210	1.93
Urea	60	0	60	6	1.4	261	1.95
Urea	30	30	60	24	2.5	289	2.13
Urea (neem cake coated)	60	0	60	33	3.1	405	2.14
Urea (farmyard manure coated)	60	0	60	23	2.5	245	1.98
Urea supergranule	60	0	60	40	3.5	429	2.12
Granulated compost	60	0	60	22	2.4	241	1.96
Urea (lac-coated)	60	0	60	33	3.1	423	2.11
CD 5%					0.1	27	0.09

Cropping systems

Fertilizer nitrogen management in wheat - summer mung - rice crop rotation

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Rice - wheat is the most common crop rotation followed by farmers in the Punjab because it produces high yields. As the rice - wheat area has increased, pulse production has declined. Pulse production can be increased by planting a wheat - summer mung - rice rotation using G-65 mung, which matures in 60 days.

We studied a wheat - summer mung - rice rotation in 1979-80 rabi with the objective of increasing pulse production and using mung straw as green manure to provide nitrogen to rice.

The crops were grown at the PAU farm in loamy sand soil, with pH 8.2 and 0.17% O.C. Immediately after wheat was harvested in mid-Apr, the field was irrigated and mung G-65 at 20 kg/ha was sown between the wheat rows. The mung crop depended on residual fertility after the wheat crop, which received 120 kg N, 26 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha. The mung crop matured the 4th week of Jun, which

Grain and straw yield of mung and mung straw nitrogen content, Ludhiana, India.

Item	1980	1981	1982	Mean
Grain yield of mung (t/ha)	0.84	0.85	0.89	0.86
Fresh weight of mung straw (t/ha)	7.6	7.6	7.5	7.6
Dry weight of mung straw (t/ha)	4.6	4.6	4.5	4.6
N content of mung straw (%)	2.16	2.21	2.26	2.21
N added through straw (kg/ha)	99.4	101.7	101.7	100.9

coincided with the beginning of the monsoon when farmers generally do not have enough covered space to keep the produce before it is dried and threshed. The pods were manually picked and mung straw was incorporated 1 day before rice was transplanted.

Average mung yield was 0.86 t/ha. Mung straw weighed 7.6 t fresh weight/ha and 4.6 t dry weight/ha, which added 101 kg N/ha to the soil (see table).

The figure shows that green manuring with mung straw 1 day before rice transplanting produced higher rice yields than using 60 kg N/ha where mung straw was removed. Mung straw and 60 kg N/ha

produced rice yields equal to those with 120 kg N/ha in treatments where mung straw was removed. □

Effect of summer mung straw green manure on rice yield, 1980-82.